

Synthesis of Some N³-Aryl (or Heteroaryl)-Azo-1,2,3-Benzotriazin-4-ones

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A series of N³-aryl (or heteroaryl)-azo-1,2,3-benzotriazin-4-ones was prepared by coupling of 3H-1,2,3-benzotriazin-4-one with a series of aromatic or heteroaromatic diazonium salts. The coupling was found to occur at the N³ atom.

FOUR tautomeric structures can be discussed for the unsubstituted 1,2,3-benzotriazin-4-one system. Two of them are the 1H and 3H tautomers, the 4-OH tautomer and the zwitterionic structure. The 4-hydroxy form could be excluded¹ owing to an intensive carbonyl band in the ir spectra. It has also been shown in a recent study² using X-ray crystallographic analysis that the unsubstituted 1,2,3-benzotriazin-4-one crystallizes as the 3H-tautomer (Ia).

A large number of substituted 1,2,3-benzotriazin-4-ones were prepared by alkylation or acylation of Ia. In general³, substitution occurs at the nitrogen atom in position 3. Only a few O-alkylated-1,2,3-benzotriazines⁴ or N²-alkylated-1,2,3-benzotriazin-ium betains^{5,6} are known and these compounds were isolated along with the N³-substituted-1,2,3-benzotriazin-4-one products. It has also been reported^{7,8} that the acetyl or benzoyl derivative of Ia was prepared by the reaction of its sodium salt (Ib) with the appropriate acid chloride. These compounds were formulated as lactam (N³-acyl) rather than lactim (O-acyl) derivatives.

Ia X = H

Ib X = Na

Ar(Het-Ar) - N=N ⁺ BF ₄ ⁻
Ia Ar phenyl
b o-Cl-phenyl
c m-Cl-phenyl
d p-Cl-phenyl
e p-CH ₃ -phenyl
f o-OCH ₃ -phenyl
g o-NO ₂ -phenyl
h p-NO ₂ -phenyl
i 1-OH-2-naphthyl
j Het-Ar benzothiazolyl
k benzimidazolyl
-F ₄ B ⁺ N=N-C ₆ H ₄ -N=N ⁺ BF ₄ ⁻

III

We report here the reaction of Ia or its sodium salt Ib with a series of aromatic or heteroaromatic diazonium tetrafluoroborates where we were able, in both cases, to isolate the same products indicating that the ambident anion (N-C-O)⁻ of Ia or Ib reacted exclusively at the N³-atom. The structure of all the N³-aryl (or heteroaryl)-azo-1,2,3-benzotriazin-4-ones (IVa-k) produced was determined on the basis of microanalytical data as well as ir spectra. The ir spectra of the products IVa-k indicate the absence of the N-H band at 3140 cm⁻¹ (characteristic of Ia), the presence of a band between 1700-1685 cm⁻¹ for C=O group (1695 cm⁻¹ in case of Ia) and a strong band between 1600-1575 cm⁻¹ characteristic of the azo group. The ir spectrum of IVi exhibits the OH band at 3510 cm⁻¹ (intramolecularly H-bonded) and that of IVk shows the N-H band of the benzimidazole moiety at 3290 cm⁻¹. When two moles of Ia or Ib were reacted with one mole of p-phenylene diamine diazonium tetrafluoroborate, the coupling proceeded normally to give the bis-diazo product V.

IVa-j

V

Experimental

All melting points reported are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP 200G spectrophotometer using KBr discs.

1,2,3-Benzotriazin-4-one (Ia) and its sodium salt (Ib): Anthranilamide (13.6 g; 0.1 mole) in acetic acid-water mixture (1 : 3) was treated with 0.1 mole of sodium nitrite (6.9 g/10 ml water) dropwise with stirring at 3-5°. The precipitated yellow product was filtered off, washed with water and⁹ crystallized

TABLE 1—ARYL (OR HETEROARYL) DIAZONIUM TETRAFLUOROBORATES

Compound	Ar(or Het-Ar)	Dec. point	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
IIa	Phenyl	105	C ₆ H ₅ N ₂ BF ₄	37.61 (37.50)	2.52 (2.60)	14.49 (14.58)
IIb	<i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl	130	C ₆ H ₄ N ₂ BF ₄ Cl	31.56 (31.78)	1.71 (1.76)	12.26 (12.36)
IIc	<i>m</i> -Cl-phenyl	167	C ₆ H ₄ N ₂ BF ₄ Cl	31.49 (31.78)	1.87 (1.76)	12.48 (12.36)
II d	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl	169	C ₆ H ₄ N ₂ BF ₄ Cl	31.84 (31.78)	1.72 (1.76)	12.51 (12.36)
IIe	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ -phenyl	120	C ₇ H ₇ N ₂ BF ₄	40.54 (40.77)	3.60 (3.39)	18.71 (19.59)
II f	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	155	C ₇ H ₇ N ₂ OBF ₄	37.65 (37.83)	3.07 (3.15)	12.50 (12.61)
II g	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	112	C ₆ H ₄ N ₂ O ₂ BF ₄	30.50 (30.37)	1.46 (1.68)	17.50 (17.72)
II h	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	191	C ₆ H ₄ N ₂ O ₂ BF ₄	30.61 (30.37)	1.72 (1.68)	17.80 (17.72)
II i	1-OH-2-naphthyl	113	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ OBF ₄	46.71 (46.51)	2.67 (2.71)	10.99 (10.85)
II j	Benzothiazolyl	120	C ₇ H ₄ N ₂ SBF ₄	33.62 (33.73)	1.54 (1.60)	16.80 (16.86)
II k	Benzimidazolyl	188	C ₇ H ₄ N ₄ BF ₄	36.41 (36.20)	2.09 (2.15)	24.82 (24.13)
III		152	C ₆ H ₄ N ₄ B ₂ F ₈	23.61 (23.52)	1.43 (1.90)	18.24 (18.30)

TABLE 2—N⁶-ARYL (OR HETEROARYL)-AZO-1,2,3-BENZOTRIAZIN-4-ONES (IVa—k) AND bis-DIAZO DERIVATIVE (V)

Compound	Ar(or Het-Ar)	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
IVa	Phenyl	238	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₄ O	62.27 (62.15)	3.67 (3.58)	27.79 (27.88)
IVb	<i>o</i> -Cl-phenyl	152	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₄ OCl	54.48 (54.64)	2.81 (2.80)	24.48 (24.51)
IVc	<i>m</i> -Cl-phenyl	127	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₄ OCl	54.52 (54.64)	2.77 (2.80)	24.70 (24.51)
IVd	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl	138	C ₁₁ H ₇ N ₄ OCl	54.71 (54.64)	2.71 (2.80)	24.37 (24.51)
IVe	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ -phenyl	108	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O	63.26 (63.39)	4.22 (4.15)	26.56 (26.41)
IVf	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	237	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂	59.69 (59.78)	3.85 (3.91)	25.07 (24.91)
IVg	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	246	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂	52.77 (52.70)	2.81 (2.70)	28.46 (28.37)
IVh	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -phenyl	235	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂	52.81 (52.70)	2.61 (2.70)	28.50 (28.37)
IVi	1-OH-2-naphthyl	212	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂	64.49 (64.35)	3.60 (3.47)	22.16 (22.08)
IVj	Benzothiazolyl	300	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₄ SO	54.68 (54.54)	2.70 (2.59)	27.13 (27.27)
IVk	Benzimidazolyl	300	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₄ O	57.79 (57.73)	3.00 (3.09)	33.78 (33.67)
V		288	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ N ₁₀ O ₂	56.71 (56.60)	3.00 (2.88)	32.84 (33.01)

from ethanol as needles, m.p. 220° (dec.)^o, yield 12 g. The benzotriazinone Ia (7.5 g) in warm ethanol was treated with sodium ethoxide (1.2 g sodium in 100 ml ethanol). After standing overnight at room temperature ethanol was removed *in vacuo* and trituration of the residue with dry toluene gave the sodium salt Ib (9.0 g) as white solid.

Aryl (or Het-Ar) diazonium tetrafluoroborates IIa-k and III: A cold solution (0-5°) of aromatic or heteroaromatic amine (0.1 mole) in HBF₄ (50 ml) was treated dropwise with sodium nitrite (0.15 mole

in minimum amount of water). The reaction mixture was stirred at 0-5° for ~0.5 hr. The precipitated diazonium salt was filtered off, washed with water and ethanol, dried and preserved in dark bottles in the cold. The diazonium salt of *p*-phenylene diamine was similarly prepared by using 2.5 equivalents of sodium nitrite to give III.

N⁶-Aryl (or heteroaryl)-azo-1,2,3-benzotriazin-4-ones (IVa-k): Ia (0.05 mole) or its sodium salt Ib in alcoholic sodium hydroxide (20 ml 25% NaOH + 40 ml ethanol) was treated under efficient stirring

with 0.6 mole of the diazonium salt at room temp. After addition, the reaction mixture was stirred for another 2 hr and left to stand for 48 hr at room temp. It was then evaporated *in vacuo* and the residual mass was washed with water, triturated with petroleum ether 40-60° and then crystallized from the appropriate solvent. The *bis*-diazo compound was similarly prepared by reacting 2 moles of Ia or Ib with III.

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